

TRUSS-BASED 3D TEXTILE-REINFORCED CONCRETE BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

This paper demonstrates the development of lightweight textile-reinforced concrete (TRC) trusses. The innovative element expands the boundaries of the traditional TRC structures towards a new standard of sustainability in the field of constructive concrete structures. The proposed TRC trusses are composed of high-performance concrete (HPC) matrix and three-dimensional (3D) textiles. The combination provides high compressive and tensile strengths for the slender truss members and thus allows the efficiency of the truss mechanism. The experimental investigation presents the design and manufacturing processes of three truss layouts and explores their structural responses under flexural loading. The presented preliminary investigation demonstrated the efficacy of the TRC truss.

KEYWORDS

TRC; Flexural; Concrete truss; Lightweight structural elements; Irregular shape; 3D textiles

INTRODUCTION

Truss structures are characterized by an efficient distribution of the applied flexural forces by internal axial loads along the truss members. The cross-section of the truss members can be optimized such as a reduction of the total weight of the beam is obtained. In the case of steel-reinforced concrete (SRC) structures, trusses are relatively rare. It is associated with the requirement for a massive concrete cover to protect the steel reinforcement from corrosion, which makes the concept not economical or practical. Textile reinforcement can be a preferable alternative to the conventional steel reinforcement system. It is characterized by high strength and high corrosion resistance which allow reinforcing thin-walled structural elements. Sustainability requirements related to the enormous CO₂ emissions involved in the manufacturing process of Portland cement raise the potential of textile-reinforced concrete (TRC). Furthermore, the ease of textile deformability allows the production of concrete elements with complex shapes. These advantages motivated the development of the proposed TRC truss. The hypothesis of the study argues that the TRC truss can be an attractive sustainable candidate to bridge over large spans.

Textile reinforcement enables the reduction of material usage, by minimizing the thickness of the cover layer of the concrete and by shaping the textiles into the complex geometries of the truss. Moreover, textiles provide the tensile post-cracking longevity of the TRC element by bridging over cracks and controlling their width (Peled et al., 2017). The production process of TRC elements should consider their tendency to unravel or transform their shape during casting, which is usually handled by applying post-processing procedures such as coating. Coating stabilizes the textile's structure and simplifies the casting process. It also provides full utilization of the cross-sectional area of the yarn (Messori et al., 2018). Another solution to rigid the reinforcement system is to use 3D textiles. Recent studies reported that 3D textiles are efficient in the casting process and, compared to several 2D textile layers, they enhance the mechanical performance of the element (El Kadi et al., 2019; Haik et al., 2017).

TRC structures are commonly found in two- or three-dimensional thin-walled components, usually reinforced with 2D textiles (Hawkins, 2019; Laiblová et al., 2018; Scheerer et al., 2017; Scholzen et al., 2015; Valeri et al., 2020). The idea of TRC truss-based beams appeared in (Nahum et al., 2023), which theoretically investigate the concept. The current study aims to bring the concept into realization by designing, constructing, and testing TRC trusses. To answer this goal, three layouts of 3D textiles were investigated and compared as potential reinforcement systems.

The current investigation focuses on the construction feasibilities and the macro-flexural behaviour of the TRC trusses. Such an experimental investigation opens the way to future and enhanced studies that should be performed to bring the concept into realization in the future.

The study is divided into 2 parts. The first part discusses the materials, the production process, and the flexural tests. The second part presents and discusses the results of the tests.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

This section provides detailed information about the properties of the materials that compose the TRC truss, the manufacturing process, and the testing procedures. The proposed reinforcement layouts are presented, and the designated mold is described.

Materials

Textiles

Two types of 3D textiles were used in this study, both of which are commercial products of Wilhelm-Kneitz AG. Details of the textiles are given in Table 1 and presented in Figure 1. The textiles were cut into 100 mm wide stripes according to the width of the truss. The stripes are set within the truss members following the longitudinal direction of the internal axial forces.

The first textile, '16G', contains 16 AR-glass yarns in the longitudinal warp direction and 16 AR-glass yarns in the weft direction. The second textile was used in two configurations (distinguish from each other by 90 degrees rotation): '8G' contains 8 AR-glass yarns in the longitudinal warp direction and 4 carbon yarns and 4 AR-glass yarns in the weft direction. '4G4C' contains 4 carbon yarns and 4 AR-glass yarns in the longitudinal warp direction and 8 AR-glass yarns in the weft direction.

The textiles were coated with styrene butadiene rubber (SBR) in advance.

Table 1: Mechanical and technical properties of the textiles

Textile properties	16G	8G	4G4C	
Commercial title	SITgrid 702	SITgrid 031	SITgrid 031	
Spacing distance [mm]	12	10	10	
Weight (coated) [g/m^2]	1055	304	304	
Yarn properties (warp)	AR-glass	AR-glass	AR-glass	Carbon
TEX [g/km]	2400	1200	1200	1600
Specific gravity [g/cm^3]	2.68	2.68	2.68	1.81
C.S area [mm^2]	0.9	0.45	0.45	0.88
Breaking strength [MPa]	1200	1200	1200	1700
Tensile capacity [N]	1075	537	537	1503

Figure 1: Textiles' details [mm]

Matrix

The cementitious matrix should answer three requirements:

- To handle the local compression forces that apply on the slender truss members, the matrix should be characterized by a high compressive strength.
- To allow the penetration of the fresh concrete through the 3D textiles, a fine-grained matrix is needed.
- The mixture is required to be workable enough to easily flow through the textile opening and the truss mold.

To answer the above requirements, a high-performance concrete (HPC) mixture was designed, its maximum grain size is specified as 0.6 mm, and superplasticizer was added to increase workability. The mixture constituents are specified in Table 2. The flow chart in Figure 2 describes the mixing protocol that was performed. The mixing was done using a 370 V CONTROLS mixer with 20 L capacity and a manual variable speed drive.

Table 2: Constituents of the mixture [kg/m^3]

Cement	Water	Sand	Silica fume (S.F)	Superplasticizer (S.P)
CEM I 52.5		<0.6 mm	Elkem 920	ENT11
600	240	1100	120	18

The compressive strength of the mixture, determined according to ASTM C109 (Cabinets et al., 2021), is 92.9 ± 14 MPa. The average flow degree that was obtained is 186.6% ($\pm 23\%$) according to flow tests that were conducted according to ASTM C1437 (Method, 2020).

Figure 2: Mixing protocol

Truss scheme and reinforcement layouts

A generic truss geometry was chosen for the experiment. Figure 3 presents the axial dimensions of the truss and the truss members' numbering. The external dimensions of the truss are 100x100x1025 mm and the thickness of the truss members is 15 mm. The truss members are numbered from 1 to 15 symmetrically about the truss center.

Figure 3 - Axial scheme of the TRC truss [mm]

Three reinforcement layouts were investigated. Figure 4 presents the proposed textile configuration where:

The green lines represent the tension reinforcement, provided by 16G textile. The tension reinforcement is identical for all layouts, it is positioned continuously along the tensed diagonal truss members and anchored in the adjacent upper and bottom members. An additional layer is positioned at the bottom of the truss.

The dashed red lines represent the textile reinforcement within the compressed or 'zero' truss members. These textiles indicate layouts' titles and vary according to the three textile configurations that were used: 16G, 8G, and 4G4C.

Figure 4 – Reinforcement details

Specification of the mold and the production process

Several requirements led to the design of the unique truss mold:

- Reusability – to allow serial production of several samples.
- Lightweight – to facilitate the casting process.
- Efficient disassembly mechanism – to avoid damaging the samples.
- Appropriate interaction – to provide a smooth concrete surface to the element.

The proposed mold includes 5 aluminum frame panels for the outer frame and 14 triangular polyurethane prisms that indicate the voids of the truss (see Figure 5). Considering the surface interaction between the triangular prisms and the hardened concrete, a unique pull-out technique was

developed. The extraction of the prisms is done by M10 hex-socket screws and compatible screw holes that are located underneath the center of each prism between two clamping bolts. While screwed in, the screw pushes out the prism against the bottom of the mold. To facilitate the extraction operation, the prisms were designed with a 1° draft angle that has been neglected in the stress and reinforcement ratio calculations.

Since fresh concrete chemically reacts with aluminum molds, which can lead to cracking during the demolding process, the prisms were made of sika-block (polyurethane), which provides a clean concrete surface, simplifies the extraction, and reduces the weight of the mold. The aluminum frame panels were covered with cello tape to prevent leaking and to serve as a buffer between the concrete and the aluminum. The assembly of all the parts of the mold, including the frame panels and the triangular prisms, is done by M6 and M8 hex socket screws, respectively.

Figure 5 - TRC truss mold

The manufacturing routine of the TRC trusses was carefully defined to ensure the similarity of the samples: The assembly of the mold was done in a constant order, using a defined set of tools and screwing degrees. Before castings, the mold was cleaned and dried, then generously oiled with 20W50 engine oil. Once the mold was cleaned, oiled, and assembled, the textiles were cut and placed according to the desired layout, and the concrete mixture was mixed according to a designed mixing protocol (see Figure 2). The casting operation was done in 3 steps on a vibrating table (230V Syntron V-51-D1) with a clamped 1 mm thick aluminum plate as an extension to fit the size of the truss. In addition, extra condensing was applied by a rubber hammer against the outer frame of the mold. After the casting procedure, the mold was moved to dry on a leveled table. Wet towels were placed around, and a polyethylene sheet was laid on top to ensure a moisturized environment. After 24 hours, the mold was disassembled, and the samples were moved to a curing container for at least 28 days. The water in the curing container was saturated with calcium hydroxide (3 gr per L) to prevent porosity increase. 48 hours before the test, the samples were taken out of the water to dry in a controlled room at a temperature of about 20° Celsius and 60% humidity.

Test Procedure

The flexural properties of the TRC truss were investigated in four-point bending tests. The tests were conducted using a 5982 Instron loading machine with a loading capacity of 100 kN. The crosshead speed was fixed to 0.5 mm/min to ensure a quasistatic loading. Steel cylinders were used as the loading pins and the supports. The flexural deformation at the center of the truss was measured by an ACR 1.5 Instron linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) with a measurement capacity of ± 15 mm. The data was collected using BLUEHILL software and load versus displacement curves were produced for all the samples. Two cameras were used to document the test procedure and the failure modes. The cameras were placed at about one meter from the specimen from both sides of the machine (the beams were loaded perpendicular to the loading frame). A black speckled pattern was applied on the front surface of the truss to allow an option for a DIC analysis in future research. Figure 6 presents the test setup scheme.

Figure 6: Loading setup scheme of the truss at the unloaded state

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results from the loading test are presented in Figure 7 and Table 3. Figure 7 presents load versus middle displacement for representative trusses. The current study focuses on the macro structural mechanism of the TRC truss and compares between the three truss layouts.

Figure 7: Load vs displacement of representative trusses from each layout

The macro-structural behaviour of the trusses is in good agreement with the well-known mechanical behaviour of TRC members (Aveston et al., 1971). Two states are observed: **State I** starts at the beginning of the loading and ends at the cracking load (F_{crk}). It is characterized by a linear-elastic behaviour and represents the initial resilience of the concrete matrix. **State II** starts at the first crack and ends at the ultimate load (F_{ult}). It is characterized by the formation of multiple cracks during a deflection-hardening behaviour and represents the resistance of the textile reinforcement within truss members. The slopes of the load-displacement curves are defined as the equivalent bending stiffnesses of the truss in each state ($K_{eq,1}$ and $K_{eq,2}$).

It is observed in Figure 7 and Table 3 that both the mechanical response and the loads and stiffness values are very similar. It can be assumed that the compression reinforcement does not contribute to the mechanical performance of the truss. Therefore, the compressed reinforcement layers can be considered, although it is reasonable to assume that the presence of the compression reinforcement

prevented compression failures, and a minimal reinforcement should be considered for design purposes. Additional investigation regarding compression reinforcement may be included in further research. The macro-structural responses of the three samples provide a positive indication towards the reliability and feasibility of the TRC truss. It highlights the possibility of the design and construction of TRC trusses and verifies the potential of the truss to act as a structural beam and carry flexural loads. Both the immediate deflection-hardening that is observed in state II and the distribution of cracks along the entire loading state, until failure, indicate the efficient load transfer mechanism of the truss and highlight the advantage of the truss from the material-save aspect. The relatively high standard deviation values (STDV) in Table 3 can be explained by production faults and will be further investigated.

Table 3: Averaged and SD load and stiffness parameters for the layouts

	$K_{eq,1}$ [kN/mm]	F_{crk} [kN]	$K_{eq,2}$ [kN/mm]	F_{ult} [kN]
16G	10.93 ±1.67	1.85 ±0.00	0.60 ±0.05	13.01 ±1.95
8G	9.92 ±0.39	1.62 ±0.03	0.62 ±0.02	11.77 ±2.11
4G4C	11.54 ±0.90	1.90 ±0.09	0.60 ±0.04	12.36 ±1.46

The failure mechanisms of the TRC truss are investigated in Figure 8. It is observed that the failure mechanism is either tension or shear failure, which appeared in all three layouts. The failures occurred at the tensed diagonal members (No. 7 and 9, Figure 3), usually at the upper truss joints (see Figure 8). Tension failures are obtained when the internal tension forces in the truss member exceed the tensile strength of the textile. Tension failures can be identified by the direction of crack propagation, in which the cracks are perpendicular to the truss member.

Shear failures are caused by global shear stresses that evolve due to the monolithic body of the truss. The rigid truss joints lead to transferring internal bending moments and shear loads between the truss members. It results in stress concentrations that lead to cracking at the joints. It is observed that the shear failures appear at the shear zones (between the load and the support).

Figure 8: Failure modes of the TRC truss: (a) tension failure; (b) shear failure

CONCLUSIONS

The current paper presents a preliminary demonstration of TRC truss beams reinforced with 3D textiles. The general response of the structural composite was investigated in four-point bending tests, and the feasibility of using 3D textiles to reinforce a concrete truss element has been proven. It is shown that TRC trusses can be successfully manufactured and serve as an efficient structural element. According to the similar flexural responses of the three layouts it can be concluded that compression reinforcement does not appear to contribute to the general flexural performance of the truss beam. To provide guidelines for the design and manufacturing of TRC truss beams, further investigation is considered.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper

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